

**QASSOBCHILIK HAMDA TIKUVCHILIK ASOSIDA
SHAKLLANGAN XALQ MAQOLLARI TAHLILI**

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Annatsiya Xalqimiz o'z avlodiga insoniyat tarixidagi eng ibratli fazilatlar meros bo'lishini orzu qilgan va hozir ham shunday. Bu oliy tilak xalqimizning maqol-u topishmoqlari, afsona va rivoyatlari, latifa-yu loflari, xalq qo'shiqlari, termalari, ertak-u dostonlari, askiya va allalari kabi bebaho durdonalarida o'zining yorqin ifodasini topgan. Hech ikkilanmay aytish mumkinki, xalqimizning barcha fazilati, falsafasi, dunyoqarashi, turli hayotiy vaziyatlarga munosabati o'zbek xalq maqollarida aks etgan. Vatan va vatanparvarlik, mehnatsevarlik, halollik, to'g'rilik, yaxshilik, adolat va insof, do'stlik, tinchlik, mardlik va jasurlik, donolik, ilm-hunar, tarbiya va odat, odo-axloq, mehmon va mehmondo'stlik, go'zallik, kamtarlik, baxt va omad, sabr-qanoat, muhabbat, oila va qo'shnichilik, umid va ishonch, erk va ozodlik, or-nomus, g'urur, samimiylik, vaqt va fursat qadri, yoshlik va qarilik haqidagi maqollar ana shular jumlasidandir.

Kalit so'zlar: maqol, temirchilik, tegirmon, to'qimachilik, kulolchilik, chilangarlik, miskarlik, zargarlik, shishasozlik va duradgorlik...

1. Hunari yo`q erkakdan,
Ignasi bor xotin yaxshi.
2. Hunarsizning qirqimi yo`q,
Hunarlining – bichimi.
3. Yetimchadan boy chiqsa,
Ayron bermas icharga.
Tikuvchidan boy chiqsa,
Qaychi bermas bicharga.
4. Tikkan chevar emas,
Bichgan – chevar.
5. Tikadigan beka bo`lsin,
Qiyadigan **cho`ri** bo`lsin.
6. Chechanning – tili,
Chevarning – qo`li.

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

Tikuvchilik – kasb-hunar turi; kiyim-kechak, ko`rpa-to`shak va boshqa buyumlarni tikish kasbi. Tikuvchilik vositalari, material va texnikasi turli davrlarda turli xalqlarning moddiy va madaniy saviyasi, iqlim sharoiti, ehtiyoj va imkoniyatlari, urf-odatlarini zaminida taraqqiy etgan. Arxeologik qazishlar natijasida turli mamlakatlar hududidan topilgan tikuvchilik vositalari, kiyim-kechak va uy-ro`zg`or buyumlari bu kasbning barcha xalqlarda qadimdan mavjudligi, o`ziga xos taraqqiyot bosqichlarini o`taganligini ko`rsatadi. XIX asrgacha barcha xalqlarda, jumladan, O`rta Osiyo xalqlarida ham tikuvchilik ishlari qo`lda bajarilgan. Ba`zi sohalarda bu kasb namunalari yuksak san`at darajasiga ko`tarilgan. Turli davrlarda tikuvchilikdan mustaqil kasb sifatida etikdo`zlik, po`stindo`zlik, mahsido`zlik, do`ppido`zlik, kashtado`zlik, gilando`zlik va boshqa ko`plab kasb turlari ajralib chiqqan. O`zbekistonda tikuvchilik hunarmandchilikdan yengil sanoatning yirik tarmog`iga aylandi.

Hunari yo`q erkakdan, ignasi bor xotin yaxshi. Maqol majoziy ma`noda qo`llangan. Azaldan xalq orasida “Bit yigitga qirq hunar oz” degan naql mavjud. Erkak kishi oilani tebratishi uchun har tomonlama mukammal bo`lishi, har ishda ilg`or, tajribali bo`lishi talab etiladi. Boqimanda er bo`lgandan ko`ra qo`lida gulday hunari bor ayol afzal. Aslini olganda, bu maqol er kishining shaxsiyati, oriyatiga nisbatan otilgan toshday ko`rinadi. Qo`lida biror hunari bor ayol ro`zg`or tebratdi degani – er kishining nomusi o`lganidir.

Chechanning – tili, chevarning – qo`li. Chevar kishi qo`l mehnati orqali kundalik turmushini kechiradi. Chechan, gapga usta, so`zamol odam tili bilan shuhrat topsa, chevar esa qo`li bilan tikkan kiyimlari, qilgan ishlari bilan obro` orttiradi, boshqalardan ajralib turadi.

2. 7. Qassobchilik asosida shakllangan xalq maqollari

Qassob – 1. Mol so`yuvchi va go`sht bilan savdo qiluvchi odam.

2. Kasb oti.

1. Qassob ustixonni o`z do`stiga sotar.

2. Qo`yni qassob so`ysin,

O`likni **g`assol** yuvsin.

3. Qo`y qassob qo`lida halol.

4. Qo`yni qassob so`ysin.

Oltinni zargar so`ksin.

5. Chumchuq so`ysa ham qassob so`ysin.

6. Qo`yingni qassobga so`ydir,

O`likni **murdasho`y**ga yuvdir.

7. Qassob oshnasiga ham suyak sotadi.

8. Qo`yni qassob so`ysin,

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

Oshni oshpaz pishirsin.

9. Qassob tanishini tuzlar.

10. Qassobning oshnasi bo`lmas.

11. Qassobga mol qayg`u, echkiga jon qayg`u.

12. Qassobning tushiga echki kirar.

13. Qassobning ko`zi – semizda,

Chanqoqning ko`zi – qimizda.

14. Qassobda sening gaping.

Baqqolda mening gapim.

15. Keksa qassob tushiga tunda mingta qo`y kirar.

16. Bolta tushguncha kunda dam olar,

Qassob kelguncha qo`y.

17. Ustalik joy bitar,

Qassoblik joy yitar.

18. Echkining ajali yetsa, qassobni suzar.

19. Qo`yingni qassobga so`ydir,

O`likni murdasha`yga yuvdir.

20. Suyak g`ajigan kuchuk qassob boltasining tagida o`lar.

21. Qassob ko`p bo`lsa, qo`y harom o`lar.

22. **Bo`rdoqi yeyman desang, qizingni qassobga ber.**

24. **Allop** un yalar, qassob – qon.

25. Echkiga jon qayg`usi,

Qassobga – moy.

26. Qassobga oq qo`y ham, qora qo`y ham bir.

27. Qassobga go`sht qayg`usi,

Echkiga jon qayg`usi.

28. Chanqoqning ko`zi qimizda,

Qassobning ko`zi – semizda.

29. Qassobga yog` qayg`usi, echkiga jon qayg`usi.

30. Qassob ustixonni o`z do`stiga sotar.

31. Qassob moy qayg`usida,

Echki jon qayg`usida.

Qassobning oshnasi bo`lmas maqolida ilgari surilgan g`oya: qassob o`z foydasi yo`lida qing`ir ishdan ham toymaydi, ya`ni o`z foydasi yo`lida o`zining

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

yaqin odamlariga, oshna-og`aynilariga ham suyak sotadi. Bundan kelib chiqadiki, qassobning ko`ngli yaqin oshnasi bo`lmaydi¹.

Qassobga mol qayg`u, echkiga jon qayg`u maqoli orqali zolimlar o`z manfaatlarini yo`lida mazlumlarni har taraflama ezadilar, butun jabr-u zulmlarni o`tkazadilar, hatto ularning o`lib ketgani bilan ham ishlari bo`lmaydi degan ma`noda pul, mol-dunyo orttirishga hirs qo`ygan odam o`z foydasi yo`lida har qanday qabohat ishlardan ham qaytmaydi, insof-u iymonni unutadi, odamlarni ular tanishmi yo begona, baribir “chuv” tushirish, qanday bo`lmasin, ulardan biror foyda ko`rib qolish fikrida bo`ladi degan ma`noda ishlatadilar².

Qassob onasiga ham suyak sotadi maqolida qassoblarning aksariyati qalloblik bilan ish ko`rgani, go`shtga suyak qo`shib sotgani, tarozidan “urib” qolgani uchun kishilar ularni azaldan birovning haqiga xiyonat qiluvchi, noinsaf shaxslar deb bilganlar.

Qassob ustixonni o`z do`stiga sotar. Qassobning asosiy maqsadi foyda olish hisoblanadi. Bu yo`lda u hech narsadan qaytmaydi. Hattoki, eng yaqin oshnasiga ham go`sht ustixonini sotaveradi. Ushbu maqolni majoziy ma`noda faqat o`z foydasini o`ylovchi, takabbur, xudbin insonlarga nisbatan ishlatish mumkin.

Echkiga jon qayg`usi, qassobga - moy. Qassobning ko`zi doim semiz hayvonlarda bo`ladi. Echki qachon bo`lmasin, baribir, o`lishini biladi. Shuning uchun doimo jon qayg`usida, ya`ni oz bo`lsa ham yashash umidida bo`ladi. Qassob esa “tayyor” bo`lgan molni so`yib, foyda olish niyatida bo`ladi. Har kim o`ziga kerak bo`lgan narsa dardida bo`ladi.

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